

**A STUDY ON EFFECTIVENESS OF TIME MANAGEMENT
AMONG STUDENTS IN DHANALAKSHMI SRINIVASAN
ENGINEERING COLLEGE, PERAMBALUR**

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Abstract:

The purpose of this research article is to evaluate the student's satisfaction towards the time management rendered by the Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College. The researcher conducted a literature search on time management of Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College interviewing of its 230 students (128 Male and 102 Females) and thoroughly scrutinized how it caters to the time needs of the inhabitants of Bareilly Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College. The study also focused on various factors that determine the students' satisfaction like students' behavior, managing time, student's performance, infrastructure facility and other value added services. Analysis was made by using various tools like percentage Analysis. The result showed that there was a significant relationship between the variable of student's satisfaction and time management of the Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College and the students have highly satisfaction of using time management effectively.

Introduction:

Time is an essential resource every student needs to achieve the goals and objectives of they are carrier. It is so delicate that it cannot be saved but can only be spent and once misused it can never be regained. Every student is looking for ways to improve time management. Whether it is the management of an organization looking for Study improvement or an individual looking for ways to better spend their time, time management is important to both.

Performance in a carrier revolves round the monetary time, efficiency (i.e. ability to do something well or achieve a desired result without wasted effort) and effectiveness (i.e. doing the right things more than performing them efficiently). As a student, both the time and study must be properly managed and all priorities must be placed in their importance. Time management involves investing time to determine what one wants out of his day to day activities. Effective time management is the investment of time in such a way that suitable results are achieved from activities within a specific time range and it emphasizes on effectiveness rather than efficiency. One's ability to choose between the important and the unimportant and be determined to follow the correctly chosen sequence is the key determinant of effectiveness in time management. In order to manage time, students must be creative and introduce various ways of producing output within a stipulated time. They must be able to manage their exams and assignments i.e. they must be able to minimize the time they spend chatting with friends and time wasting activities.

Review of Literature:

Ramakrishnan (2017) in this Paper the author briefly describe a system for forms-based, workflow management that helps members of a software development team overcome geographical barriers to collaboration. Our system, called the Web Integrated Software Environment (WISE), is implemented as a World- Wide- Web service that allows for management and measurement of software development projects based on dynamic analysis of change activity in the workflow.

Komiya (2017) the authors aim at constructing an integrated software project management system with an object database. This paper describes a process model for software project management that forms the basis of the system. This paper also describes a framework for inducing the sequence of operations that the project manager must perform: issuing instructions to workers in accordance with a plan based on the process model, progress evaluation based on progress reports sent from the workers, and analysis of the impacts of any problems detected.

Bani Ali (2017) this study surveyed 497 project management software users in a wide variety of project-driven organizations to examine the relationships among: computer self-efficacy, information quality, system functionality, ease of use, project complexity, performance impact, organization size, project size, and user education, training and experience level.

Min Tjoa (2016) this paper has a Data Warehouse (DWH) contains a large amount of aggregated data, collected from the various operational, enterprise-wide data sources. The DWH will be logical modeled as a

virtual n-dimensional data-cube. Analyses against this n-dim data-cube allow the decision makers (e.g. executives, middle management, controllers, etc.) to view their enterprise in various different ways.

Edwin Morris (2015) this paper explains today's rapidly changing environment it is no longer possible for isolated systems to provide all the capabilities that are necessary to fulfill a mission. Therefore, there is an increasing trend towards interconnected systems of systems that provide capabilities not available in a single system.

Research Methodology:

Respondents were asked to give on different aspects of students satisfaction towards the time management in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College and the questionnaire was related with the aid of three liker scaled subjects ranging between one and three 1 = No, 2 = Sometimes, 3 = Yes.

Statement of Problem:

In order to reach the set objectives thought the availability of literature the researchers stated the problem as students satisfaction towards Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College Perambalur.

Objective of Study:

- To know the effective time management helps to achieve of goals.
- How the effective time management is develop your academic performance.
- To identify the time useless activities during the class hours.

Limitations of Study:

- The survey has been conducted only on 230 respondents (128 males and 102 females).
- The accuracy of findings of study depends upon the correctness of the responses provided by the respondents.
- UN willingness of some respondents to provide information to another limitation.
- Finding of study may be influenced by personal bias of the respondents.
- Significance of Study
- It's highly essential for us to collect student's feedback on various departments; this would stand useful in enabling students to take positive step to maintain time management. Indeed the students for overall effectiveness in future definitely count on the self evaluation on their performance.

Method of Data Collection:

A descriptive research Design was adopted from the study. It accounts for both primary and secondary data. Primary source of data were collected from students through structure by the way of questionnaire secondary data the collected from books and websites.

Sampling Techniques and Size:

Sampling is a technique or method of selection of samples simple sampling method is used. The researches has taken (138 males and 102 female) samples from students of Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College Perambalur.

Tools Used:

The primary data were analyzed with the help of percentage.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Age Wise Classification

S.No	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Under 18	28	12
2	18 to 20	124	54
3	Above 20	78	34
	Total	230	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

From the above table it is observed that, 12 % of respondents are under 18 years, 54 % of respondents are 18 to 20 years and 34% of respondents are above 20 years.

Table 2: Gender Wise Classification

S.No	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Male	128	56
2	Female	102	44
	Total	230	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

From the above table it is observed that the highest 56 % are male and 44 % of the respondents are female.

Table 3: College on Time Classification

S.No	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Yes	150	65
2	No	33	14
3	Sometimes	47	21
	Total	230	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

The above table it is observed that, 65% of respondents are yes, 14% of respondents are no, and 21% of respondents are sometimes.

Table 4: Manage the Time Properly

S.No	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Yes	120	52
2	No	40	17
3	Sometimes	70	31
	Total	230	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

From the above shows that, 52% of respondents are say yes to manage time properly, 17% of respondents are say no to manage time properly, and 31% of respondents only say sometimes on manage the time properly.

Table 5: Time Balances between Family Life and Study Time

S.No	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Yes	109	47
2	No	46	20
3	Sometimes	75	33
	Total	230	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

From the table shows that, 47% of respondents says yes to time balance between family life and study time, 20% of respondents says no to time balance between family life and study time, and 33% of respondents says only sometimes to balance the time between family life and study time.

Table 6: Effective Time Management

S.No	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Agree	106	46
2	Neutral	84	37
3	Disagree	40	17
	Total	230	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

From the table express that, 46% of respondents says agree that they effective time management, 37% of respondents says neutral that they effective time management, and 17% of respondents says disagree that the effective time management.

Table 7: Time Management Increase Academic Performance

S.No	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Agree	119	52
2	Neutral	76	33
3	Disagree	35	15
	Total	230	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

From the table express that, 52% of respondents say agree that time management increase academic performance, 33% of respondents say neutral that time management increase academic performance, and 15% of respondents say disagree that time management increase academic performance.

Table 8: Time Management in Personal Life

S.No	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Yes	128	56
2	No	54	23
3	Sometimes	48	21

	Total	230	100
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Source: Primary Data

Inference:

From the table express that, 56% of respondents say yes that time management help in personal life, 23% of respondents say no that time management will not help in personal life, and 21% of respondents say that only sometimes time management will help in personal life.

Table 9: Time is Equal to Money

S.No	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Yes	144	63
2	No	86	37
	Total	230	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

From the table express that, 63 % of respondents say yes that time is equal to money and 37 % of respondents say no that time is not equal to money.

Table 10: Poor Time Management Affects Quality of Study

S.No	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Yes	100	43
2	No	54	23
3	Sometimes	76	34
	Total	230	100

Source: Primary data

Inference:

From the table express that, 43% of respondents say yes for the poor time management will affect quality of study, 23% of respondents say no for the poor time management will not affect the quality of study, and 34% of respondents say only sometimes the poor time management will affect quality of study.

Findings:

- Majority 54% of the respondents are under the age of 18 to20 years old.
- Majority 56% of respondents are males.
- Majority 54% of respondents are Hostellers.
- Majority 53% of respondents are satisfied with the study hours in the college.
- Majority 65% of respondents are come to college on time.
- Majority 58% of respondents are completed the task within one week.
- Majority 52% of respondents are felt there performance is good when time is managed properly.
- Majority 47% of respondents are agreed that they are able to maintain time balance between family time and study time.
- Majority 47% of respondents are agreed that they have enough break sin between the studies.
- Majority 53% of respondents are agreed that they have enough time to relax themselves.
- Majority 41% of respondents are agreed that they are wasting time by chatting with the friends.
- Majority 46% of respondents are agreed that effective time management improve the outputs.
- Majority 42% of respondents are agreed that college performances us ceptible took affected by poor management.
- Majority 52% of respondents are agreed that effective time management improve the academic performance.
- Majority 56% of respondents are agreed that time management helpful for their personal life.
- Majority 42% of respondents are in a neutral state that lack of time management is one of the biggest problems in studies.
- Majority 40% of respondents are agreed that they have schedules or priorities in executing the work.
- Majority 49% of respondents are satisfied with the time schedule of our college.
- Majority 63% of respondents are agreed that time is equal to money.
- Majority 43% of respondents are agreed that the poor time management affect the quality of their study.
- Majority 43% of respondents are agreed that they can succeed with the enormous benefits of time management.
- Majority 49% of respondents are agreed that they ask dead time for the extra responsibility in our previous job.

Conclusion:

Effect time management is a panacea to organizational effectiveness and not a place Bo. Effective time management will improves off productivity, make scheduling of jobs easier, make staffs opera form tasks at their highest skill level, helping staff to prioritize and accomplish important task, recording and guiding the organization towards achieving its set goals. Being well organized in respect of the use of time does not necessary eansa fixed state of quality There search found out that majority of the organization work force are young, single, highly educated and has been working for a short time, this shows that the organization is in the process of rebranding and lots initiatives has been taken into account.

Suggestions:

Give priorities to the important work. Schedule your work according to the preferences. Set up Deadlines for task. Maintain positive attitude towards everything. Avoid doing Multi task; it will reduce your confidences. Take Regular Breaks in between your work. Motivate Yourself.

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